

Hydrogen and Methane Production from Food Residue Biomass Product (FORBI)

I. Michalopoulos¹, G.M. Lytras¹, D. Mathioudakis¹, C. Lytras¹, A. Goumenos¹, I. Zacharopoulos¹,
K. Papadopoulou^{1*}, G. Lyberatos^{1,2}

¹School of Chemical Engineering, National Technical University of Athens Iroon Polytechniou 9, Zografou 157 80, Athens, Greece

²Institute of Chemical Engineering Sciences (ICE-HT), Stadiou Str., Platani, 26504 Patras, Greece

*corresponding author: e-mail: kpapado@chemeng.ntua.gr, +30 2107723115

Abstract

This study concerns the production of hydrogen and methane from a Food Residue Biomass (FORBI) product [1], generated from pre-sorted HFW in a CSTR and in a PABR respectively. FORBI is generated by drying and shredding the fermentable fraction of household food waste collected door-to-door in the Municipality of Halandri, Greece.

Hydrogen production from FORBI through anaerobic fermentation under acidogenic mesophilic conditions was carried out using a 4L CSTR, operated at 12 h HRT under an organic loading of 15 g TS·L⁻¹. The H₂-CSTR was operated for 40 days. During the operation of H₂-CSTR the production of biogas reached up to 0,1026 L_{biogas}·g_{FORBI}⁻¹ and the percentage of hydrogen in the gas up to 48,2 %.

The conversion of FORBI into methane was carried out through the operation of a 77L PABR operated under mesophilic methanogenic conditions at various operating parameters (OLR, HRT, T). Two different approaches were adopted for the pre-treatment of the feedstock. For the two first phases of the experimental procedure, a liquid extraction step was carried out before feeding the bioreactor with the separated liquid fraction, while in the subsequent three phases, a whole suspension of FORBI was used as feed. The mean biogas production rate was 0,158±0,02 L_{biogas}·g_{FORBI}⁻¹ and the mean methane percentage in the biogas was 67,5±2,1%, in the first two phases. The mean biogas production rate was 0,519±0,03 L_{biogas}·g_{FORBI}⁻¹ and the mean methane percentage in the biogas was 66±2,8%, when a whole suspension of FORBI was fed to the PABR.

Statement of Novelty

The present work, pursued under the framework of the Horizon2020 project WASTE4think, focuses on investigating the anaerobic digestion and dark fermentation potential of a biomass product (named FORBI: Food Residue Biomass) for the production of biofuels (biomethane and biohydrogen respectively). The FORBI production process includes drying and shredding of Household Fermentable Waste (HFW) and it is a promising idea since it significantly reduces the mass and volume of the HFW, it can be stored for prolonged periods of time without deteriorating, odors are eliminated and the product is homogenized.

Keywords: Methane, Hydrogen, Volatile Fatty Acids, Food Residue Biomass, Dark Hydrogen Fermentation, Anaerobic Digestion, PABR.

List of Abbreviations

ABR	Anaerobic Baffled Reactor
CSTR	Continuous Stirred Tank Reactor
FORBI	Food Residue Biomass
GCV	Gross Calorific Value
GHG	Green House Gases
HFW	Household Fermentable Waste
HRT	Hydraulic Retention Time
MSW	Municipal Solid Waste
NCV	Net Calorific Value
OLR	Organic Loading Rate
PABR	Periodic Anaerobic Baffled Reactor
sCOD	soluble Chemical Oxygen Demand
T	Switching Period
tCOD	total Chemical Oxygen Demand
TSS	Total Suspended Solids

VFAs Volatile Fatty Acids
VSS Volatile Suspended Solids

37 **1 Introduction**

38 The generation and disposal of MSW is dramatically increasing in the recent years due to the rapid population growth
39 (over 9 billion by 2050) [2] and modernization throughout the world. According to a recent report, published by the
40 World Bank, currently more than 1,3 billion tons of municipal solid waste are generated annually worldwide, while
41 waste generation is expected to exceed 2,2 billion tons in the next decade [3]. Breaking down the solid waste
42 generation data, it has been proved that 30-50% of the MSW is food waste, out of which 95% is ultimately landfilled.
43 These quantities of landfilled food waste reflect a great wastage of nutrient content and energy recovery potential,
44 while at the same time landfilled food waste is a major contributor to landfill methane and other GHG emissions.
45 Moreover, the Urban Development Series of World Bank suggests that “poorly managed waste has an enormous
46 impact on health, local and global environment and the economy. In addition, improperly managed waste usually
47 results in down-stream costs higher than what it would have cost to manage the waste properly in the first place”[3].
48 Hence, policies have been developed recently, aiming at minimizing the amounts of fermentable waste ending up in
49 landfills

50 In Europe alone, 88 million tons of food is wasted, with an overall cost estimated at 143 billion Euros according to
51 the literature [4–7]. Scientific and technological developments offer a variety of valorization options and technologies
52 for the production of valuable chemicals, products and biofuels [8–10]. The exploitation of these -or some of these-
53 options could drastically minimize the amount of food waste ending up in the landfills.

54 The current research work, pursued within the framework of WASTE4think, a Horizon2020 project, is based on work
55 previously done extensively studying anaerobic digestion and fermentation of food waste [8–15]. More specifically,
56 this paper focuses on the effectiveness and benefits of using pretreated food waste (dried and shredded) as a feedstock
57 for methane (CH₄) production via anaerobic digestion and hydrogen (H₂) production via dark fermentation.

58 WASTE4think proposes an innovative management approach of the HFW that includes source separation and separate
59 collection of this fraction in the Municipality of Halandri, followed by drying and shredding of the collected waste at
60 the Municipality level. The scope of the project is to evaluate the generated product, named FORBI (Food Residue
61 Biomass) as a potential feedstock for the production of biofuels, among various valorization alternatives. FORBI is a
62 high quality homogenized and dry biomass product weighing approximately 25% of the original food waste
63 collected[1], which may be stored for prolonged periods of time without deterioration.

64 The idea of implementing a pre-treatment step to improve the characteristics of the organic waste before using it as
65 an anaerobic digestion feedstock to enhance methane production is not new. There are a lot of research papers covering
66 the specific subject both for organic waste generally and food waste more specifically for methane [16–18] and
67 hydrogen [19] production. Moreover, the combination of thermal and mechanical pre-treatment has been evaluated in
68 the past [18], however not systematically and not in a homogenized food waste product like FORBI.

69 The scope of the current research paper is to investigate the effect of drying/shredding pre-treatment and pursue an
70 initial evaluation of FORBI as feedstock for the production of biomethane and biohydrogen, respectively.

71 Methane production was carried out using a Periodic Anaerobic Baffled Reactor, a novel high-rate bioreactor designed
72 to operate at high organic loading rates. The PABR resembles a simple ABR with the compartments configured
73 circularly. Variation of the switching frequency (or equivalently the switching period (T), i.e. the time for switching
74 the feed to all compartments) allows flexibility in the operation of the PABR. The PABR can be operated as a simple
75 ABR, if the switching frequency is set to zero, and, at relatively high switching frequency, as a single-compartment
76 upflow bioreactor [20–23].

77 **2 Materials and Methods**

78 The measurements of tCOD and sCOD, TSS and VSS, total alkalinity and temperature were carried out according to
79 Standard Methods [24]. The pH and conductivity were measured using a digital pH-meter (WTW INOLAB PH720)
80 and conductivity meter (WTW INOLAB), respectively. For the quantification of VFAs, 1ml of sample acidified with
81 30µL of 20% H₂SO₄ was analyzed on a gas chromatograph (SHIMADZU GC-2010 plus) equipped with a flame
82 ionization detector and a capillary column (Agilent technologies, 30m x 0,53mm ID x 1µm film, HP-FFAP) and an
83 autosampler (SHIMADZU AOC-20s). The oven was programmed from 105 °C to 160 °C at a rate of 15 °C·min⁻¹ and
84 subsequently to 225 °C (held for 3min) at a rate of 20 °C·min⁻¹. Helium was used as the carrier gas at 30ml·min⁻¹, the
85 injector temperature was set at 230 °C and the detector at 230 °C. For the quantification of the methane content of the
86 biogas, a GC-TCD was used (Shimadzy GC-2014). The separation column's (Carboxen 1000) length was 5 m and the
87 interior diameter 2,1 mm. The initial temperature of the GC-TCD was 40 °C. For the estimation of the methane content
88 a temperature programme was used (duration: 25 mins) during which the temperature was increasing 10 °C·min⁻¹ until

89 reaching 185 °C and staying stable at this temperature for 5 minutes. The methane content then was calculated using
90 a standard calibration curve. The biogas production rate was measured using an oil displacement technique [20, 21].

91 **2.1 FORBI generation and characteristics**

92 FORBI is a biomass product generated by an alternative food waste management scheme. A GAIA GC-200 Food
93 Waste Drying Machine developed by GAIA Corp. is fed with the raw food waste collected daily and after a 9-hour
94 drying/shredding process FORBI is collected from the dryer tank.

95 The proposed HFW management scheme offers a variety of benefits, since FORBI exhibits numerous advantages:

- 96 1. The volume and weight of the processed solid feedstock is reduced by as high as 75-80% compared to the
97 initial raw food waste.
- 98 2. A homogenized product is generated, with highly repeatable physicochemical characteristics (they don't vary
99 appreciably)
- 100 3. No odors are emitted.
- 101 4. FORBI may be stored for prolonged periods without deteriorating.

102 A series of analyses had been conducted, in a previous study, to develop an in-depth characterization of FORBI [1].
103 The results show, that FORBI exhibits high homogeneity. Moreover, the bulk density of FORBI was found to be as
104 high as 690 kg·m⁻³. The basic results of the characterization of FORBI are shown in Table 2-1.

105 *Table 2-1 Direct analysis of FORBI*

Humidity (%)	1,1-1,4
Ash (%)	8,0-8,7
Volatiles (%)	75,3-78,1
Fixed carbon (%)	13,2-16,4

106 Moreover, an elemental analysis as well as an experimental determination of the NCV and GCV of FORBI are given
107 in Table 2-2

108 *Table 2-2 Elemental Analysis, NCV and GCV of FORBI*

C (%)	47,9-48,7
H (%)	6,16-6,26
N (%)	2,23-2,31
S (%)	0,13-0,16
O (%)	33,0-34,2
Cl (%)	0,45-0,55
NCV (MJ·kg⁻¹)	18,09-18,38
GCV (MJ·kg⁻¹)	19,32-19,65

109
110 **2.2 Hydrogen production experimental procedure**
111 In order to investigate the use of FORBI as feedstock for the production of biohydrogen through dark fermentation, a
112 pilot-scale CSTR was used. The CSTR had a working volume of 4L and was operated under anaerobic and mesophilic
113 conditions (35 °C). For the operation of the pilot-scale bioreactor, FORBI with particles <5 mm was used (FORBI
114 5mm).

115 Gas and liquid samples were taken routinely and analyzed for hydrogen and methane content using the same method
116 as explained before. Total Suspended Solids (TSS), Volatile Suspended Solids (VSS), and Volatile Fatty Acids
117 (VFAs) were also estimated on a regular basis. The production of biogas was also measured.

118 During start-up, the CSTR was inoculated with 1 L of thermally treated (95°C for 15 minutes) activated sludge and
119 was fed with an aquatic suspension of FORBI (15g FORBI·L⁻¹). The bioreactor was started up in batch mode for 48
120 hours (data not shown). It was then operated in a continuous mode under an HRT (hydraulic retention time) of 12
121 hours using the same aquatic suspension of FORBI. The CSTR operated without pH regulation

122 **2.3 Methane production experimental procedure**

123 The scope of the experimental procedure was to evaluate FORBI as an anaerobic digestion feedstock for methane
124 production using a pilot-scale PABR, of operating volume of 77L. Therefore, the bioreactor was operated at various

125 OLR and HRT outlined in Table 1. The PABR was equipped with sampling valves in every compartment, placed in
 126 the middle-height of the compartment. The PABR consists of two concentric cylinders, the interior of which is filled
 127 with water maintained at 35°C through temperature control.

128 The PABR was initially operated with a HRT of 12,2d and a T of 2d, with an influent tCOD of 7250mg·L⁻¹ for 86d
 129 (phase #1). After a steady periodic state was reached, the HRT was decreased to 10d and the mean influent tCOD was
 130 increased to 11690mg·L⁻¹ for an operation period of 43d (phase #2). A liquid extraction step was used as pretreatment
 131 during phases #1 and #2, feeding the bioreactor only with FORBI extract so as to keep the solids content of the feed
 132 low, a general requirement for high-rate bioreactors. Initially, FORBI was suspended in water, in a proportion of 18
 133 g_{FORBI}·L⁻¹_{water} and was vigorously stirred for 30 minutes. Then the slurry was filtered under pressure using a cloth
 134 filter. The liquid phase (filtrate) retained 36,4% of the organic content of the waste during phase #1 and 29,3% during
 135 phase #2. The solid phase collected was valorized for the production of compost.

136 After a steady periodic state was reached, the HRT was decreased to 8,7d and the PABR was fed with a mean influent
 137 tCOD of 10760mg·L⁻¹ (phase #3). During phase #3, a whole suspension of FORBI was used instead of the liquid
 138 fraction, in order to see if FORBI hydrolysis is fast enough to sustain a high-rate anaerobic digestion without solids
 139 separation. As the PABR proved to handle satisfactorily a whole FORBI suspension as a feed, for the next
 140 experimental phase (phase#4) the HRT was decreased to 5d without changing the influent tCOD (tCOD =10830 mg·L⁻¹).
 141 In phase #5, the HRT was maintained at 5d, while the tCOD in the feed was approximately doubled (22630 mg·L⁻¹).
 142 The fifth phase (phase#5) was split into two sub-phases, investigating the response of the PABR when alternating
 143 the switching frequency (T). More specifically, during phase#5.1 a sharp increase of the tCOD was implemented
 144 leading to an influent tCOD of 22630mg·L⁻¹, while the HRT was not changed. Then, after 18 days of operation the
 145 switching period was decreased from 2d to 1d without changing any other parameters (phase#5.2).

146

Table 2-3 Operating phases of the PABR

	Phase #1	Phase #2	Phase #3	Phase#4	Phase#5	
					#5.1	#5.2
Feed: Aqueous extract of FORBI	✓	✓				
Feed: Aqueous suspension of FORBI			✓	✓	✓	✓
HRT (d)	12,2	10	8,7	5	5	5
Switching period (d)	2	2	2	2	2	1
Influent tCOD (g·L⁻¹)	7,32	11,74	10,83	10,7	22,63	22,63
Organic Loading Rate (g_{COD}·L_{reactor}⁻¹·d⁻¹)	0,6	1,17	1,24	2,14	4,53	4,53
Operation Period (d)	86	41	67	56	18	23

147 3 Results and Discussion

148 3.1 Hydrogen production

149 The CSTR was operated for 30 days. During the operation the production of biogas reached up to 0.1026 L_{biogas}·
 150 g_{FORBI}⁻¹ and the maximum percentage of hydrogen was 48,2%.

151 During the operation of the bioreactor, the biogas production rate was not constant Figure 3-1 (b), despite the fact that
 152 the pH of the bioreactor remained 4,2-4,6 throughout the experiment Figure 3-1 (a). During the first 7 days, the
 153 production rate of biogas increased from 0,65 L·L_{bioreactor}⁻¹·d⁻¹ to 3,07 L·L_{bioreactor}⁻¹·d⁻¹. Afterwards, it decreased
 154 significantly and was 1,37 L·L_{bioreactor}⁻¹·d⁻¹ on the average for the rest of the period. The concentrations of the main
 155 metabolic products measured during the operation of the hydrogen producing reactor are presented in Figure 3-2. The
 156 dominant metabolic products, measured, were acetic and butyric acids, which are common for biohydrogen producing
 157 bioreactors [25]. The low concentrations of propionic acid indicate an efficient hydrogen production process, since
 158 during the formation of propionate hydrogen is consumed [14, 26].

159 The decrease of the biogas production rate after the 7th day of operation could be attributed to the consumption of
 160 hydrogen by hydrogen consuming microorganisms which consume H₂ and CO₂ to produce acetate [25]. In order to
 161 eliminate these hydrogen consuming microorganisms, the bioreactor was purged with air for one hour using an air
 162 pump (arrows in figures 1a and 1b). After each purging, the biogas production rate increased significantly but not to
 163 the level observed in the beginning of the operation.

Figure 3-1 (a) pH of CSTR vs time, (b) Biogas production rate of CSTR vs time

Figure 3-2 Concentration of metabolic products of H₂-CSTR vs time.

165 A concise literature review was carried out to compare the obtained hydrogen production with others based on food
 166 waste (Table 3-1).

167 Table 3-1 Biogas and hydrogen productivity in comparison with other studies

Pretreatment Method	Biogas Productivity (L·gvs ⁻¹)	Hydrogen Productivity (L·gvs ⁻¹)
Drying/shredding, FORBI (current study)	0,13	0,062 (48% H ₂)
Grounded in a blender, no prior sterilization (semi-batch process) [27]	0,055	0,027 (49% H ₂)
Mixed up with tap water at the volumetric ratio of 1:3 and then grinded in a food blender [28]	0,687	0,261 (38% H ₂)
Grounded in a blender, no prior sterilization [29]	0,648	0,292 (42-48% H ₂)
The feedstock was prepared by mixing raw food waste with tap water, with no other pre-treatment taking place [30]	0,171	0,067 (39% H ₂)

168 **3.2 Methane production**

169 The PABR exhibited great stability during all five phases of the process. During the stable periodic state of phase#1,
 170 the mean tCOD removal rate was 89% (Figure 3-3 b) with a mean effluent tCOD concentration of 872 mg·L⁻¹. The
 171 VSS remained below 0,5g L⁻¹ (Figure 3-3 a) in all four compartments of the PABR during the whole phase #1. The
 172 the mean biogas production rate was 0,158 L_{biogas}·g_{FORBI}⁻¹ and the mean methane composition of the biogas was 65-70%.

173 During phase #2, the OLR almost doubled from 0,59 gCOD·L_{bioreactor}⁻¹·d⁻¹ to 1,17 gCOD·L_{bioreactor}⁻¹·d⁻¹, by decreasing
 174 the HRT from 12,2d to 10d and by increasing the mean influent tCOD from 7320mg·L⁻¹ to 11690mg·L⁻¹. The mean
 175 tCOD removal rate was 93,5% (Figure 3-3 b) and the mean biogas production rate was 0,11L_{biogas}·g_{FORBI}⁻¹. The pH
 176 remained at optimum levels for methane production in all four compartments of the reactor during phases #1 and #2.
 177 The mean methane composition of the biogas was 65-70%.

178 Subsequently, the reactor was fed with a whole suspension of FORBI and operated at an HRT of 8,7d (phase#3). The
 179 feed TSS concentration was 10g·L⁻¹. The PABR responded efficiently to the change, while no problems were observed
 180 by the high solids content, that is contained in FORBI's suspension (approximately 15g·L⁻¹). The mean tCOD removal
 181 rate was 86,4%. Feeding with a whole suspension of FORBI, with all its solids content, resulted in a substantial
 182 increase of the mean biogas production rate to 0,56L_{biogas}·g_{FORBI}⁻¹. The mean methane composition of the biogas
 183 remained in the range 65-70%.

184 In the next experimental phase (phase#4) the HRT was further decreased to 5 days, while the average tCOD of the
 185 influent remained the same, leading to an organic loading rate of 2,14 gCOD·L_{bioreactor}⁻¹·d⁻¹. The PABR handled very
 186 well the decrease of the HRT. The average tCOD removal rate observed was 80,5% while the biogas productivity was
 187 0,5 L_{biogas}·g_{FORBI}⁻¹, once a stable periodic operation was established. The average methane composition of the biogas
 188 was 69,6%.

189 Finally, in the fifth phase of the experimental procedure (phase#5), the average feed tCOD was increased to
 190 22630mg·L⁻¹ leading to an organic loading rate of 4,53 gCOD·L_{bioreactor}⁻¹·d⁻¹. Again, the bioreactor's stability was very
 191 good, achieving an average tCOD removal of 85,6%, while slightly increasing the biogas productivity to 0,531
 192 L_{biogas}·g_{FORBI}⁻¹. The methane content was stable, giving an average value of 62,7%. In this phase, the VSS (Figure 3-
 193 3 a) and the VFAs (Figure 3-5) of the bioreactor were slightly increased showing kinetic limitation at this loading rate.
 194 Hence, the switching period was decreased from 2 days to 1 day to investigate the system's response to this change
 195 to the operational parameters. The result of this change was that both the VSS and the VFAs showed a slight decrease,
 196 without, however, reaching the very low levels of the previous phases.

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Figure 3-3 (a) VSS concentration vs time, (b) tCOD removal rate of PABR vs time

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Figure 3-4 Biogas production rate of PABR vs time.

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Figure 3-5 VFAs vs time, four compartments and effluent, PABR

212 Table 3-2 presents the aggregated results of the five experimental phases of the methane production are presented.

213 *Table 3-2. Methane production aggregated results*

	Phase #1	Phase #2	Phase #3	Phase #4	Phase #5	
					5.1	5.2
tCOD_{feedstock} (g·L⁻¹)	7,32	11,7	10,83	10,7	22,63	22,63
OLR (gCOD·L_{bioreactor}⁻¹·d⁻¹)	0,6	1,17	1,24	2,14	4,53	4,53
tCOD_{effluent} (g·L⁻¹)	0,87±0,02	0,79±0,02	1,86±0,01	2,03±0,02	3,44±0,03	5,43±0,04
tCOD Removal (%)	89±1,2	93,5±1,3	86,4±0,7	80,5±0,7	85,6±1,2	74,3±1,9
Biogas Productivity (L_{biogas}·L_{bioreactor}⁻¹·d⁻¹)	0,26±0,01	0,42±0,01	0,56±0,02	0,98±0,02	2,09±0,03	2,07±0,03
Productivity (L_{biogas}·kg_{FORBI}⁻¹)	158±2	110±1,8	484±2,3	500±3,1	531±3,4	517±3,3
Methane Percentage (%)	65-70	65-70	65-70	69,6±1,6	62,7±1,4	62,8±1,4

214 A literature review on the anaerobic digestion of food waste, shown that drying and shredding food waste as a
215 pretreatment method is really promising (Table 3-3)

216 *Table 3-3 Biogas and methane productivity in comparison with other studies*

Pretreatment Method	Biogas Productivity (L·gvs ⁻¹)	Methane Productivity (L·gvs ⁻¹)
Drying/shredding, FORBI (current study)	0,708	0,444 (62,5% CH ₄)
Shredded then passed to a feed preparation vessel where it was mixed with recirculated whole digestate and macerated to give a particle size less than 12 mm [31]	0,642	0,402 (62% CH ₄)
Crushed using an electrical kitchen blender and then sieved [32]	0,784	0,400 (51% CH ₄)
Co-digestion of food waste with straw[33]	0,58	0,392 (67%)

217 4 Conclusion

218 The present work concerns the production of Hydrogen and Methane from a Food Residue Biomass (FORBI) product,
219 generated from pre-sorted fermentable household waste in a CSTR and in a Periodic Anaerobic Baffled Reactor
220 (PABR) respectively. FORBI is generated by drying and shredding the fermentable fraction of household food waste
221 collected door-to-door in the Municipality of Halandri.

222 Operating at an HRT of 12 hours, the maximum production of hydrogen from FORBI was 0,1026L_{biogas}·g_{FORBI}⁻¹ with
223 a hydrogen concentration of 48,2%. Homoacetogenesis seems to have reduced the amount of hydrogen produced.
224 Short aeration of the reactor has allowed temporary increase in the biogas production rate, but it is clear that further
225 work is necessary to secure a stable and optimal hydrogen production.

226 The PABR proved an excellent high rate reactor for methane production from FORBI. The reactor was capable of
227 handling successfully a suspension of FORBI, without the need for solids removal, yielding on the average
228 0,519L_{biogas}·g_{FORBI}⁻¹ and 66% methane content. Some kinetic limitation has appeared at an organic loading of 4,53
229 gCOD·L_{bioreactor}⁻¹·d⁻¹.

230 Compared to other published works, drying and shredding food waste has proved to be a promising method in terms
231 of maximizing biogas productivity and especially when it comes to biomethane production, through anaerobic

232 digestion. Hence, FORBI apart from its benefits regarding mass and volume reduction, homogeneity and stability, is
233 an excellent feedstock for either a dark fermentation or an anaerobic digestion process.

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237

238 **References**

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